

Multivariate Bayesian spatial modelling of child labour and out of school children in Nigeria: mapping areas of excess risk

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Summary

This research implemented a Bayesian multivariate spatial model to identify areas where the risk of children being out of school, engaging in child labour, or undertaking hazardous work differs from the risk of poverty in Nigeria. Using recently released geo-coded UNICEF MICS survey data, the results showed how the spatial distribution of the three outcomes studied differ and highlighted specific areas where the excess risk for each outcome, after accounting for poverty, is high. The model was also used to predict the risk of each outcome across the whole of Nigeria at a high spatial resolution.

KEYWORDS: child labour, out of school children, Bayesian spatial modelling, multivariate modelling, Nigeria.

1 Introduction

Previously, the phenomenon of child labour has often been conflated with that of poverty, with the prevailing assumption being that children will only engage in work if they are required to for financial reasons. This argument that a child engaging in child labour is purely a consequence of a household needing another person to generate income stems from Basu and Van (1998), who used it as one of the fundamental assumptions in their theoretical model of the economics of child labour. However, more recent child labour studies have found that, while a child being from a lower income household is usually associated with an increased risk of them engaging in child labour, several other social, demographic and contextual factors can further increase this risk (e.g. Krauss, 2017). Another common assumption about children in child labour is that their work prevents them from attending school. Again, however, this is not always the case, and many children combine work and school (Enebe et al., 2021). It is important to understand how patterns of poverty, child labour and

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school attendance are similar and different, so that each phenomenon can be fully understood and interventions for specific problems can be properly targeted.

By using a spatial modelling approach, it is possible to better understand where and in what contexts the risks of child labour and school non-attendance differ from each other, and from the risk of poverty. To this end, this research implements a Bayesian multivariate spatial model based on geo-located data from UNICEF’s Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey (MICS) of Nigeria in 2021. Using this method, the spatial distribution of low-income households is used as a “baseline” outcome, with the risks of child labour and school non-attendance, as well as children in hazardous work, modelled as excess risks.

2 Data

The data source used for this research was the UNICEF Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey round 6 (MICS6) conducted in Nigeria in 2021. UNICEF has also recently released GIS packages for several of its surveys, including the Nigeria MICS6, which provide longitude and latitude co-ordinates for anonymised survey cluster centroids. To the authors’ knowledge, this study represents the first attempt to use this GIS data to analyse child labour and school attendance.

This study focused on children aged 5-14 and four dependent cluster-level variables were calculated from the MICS6 data: the number of children in the lowest wealth quintile, the number of children that were out of school, the number of children that met the threshold of hours to be engaged in child labour (according to UNICEF’s definition), and the number of children engaged in hazardous work. For clarity, the outcome of meeting the threshold of hours to be engaged in child labour is hereafter referred to as “child labour” and this does not include children engaging in hazardous work for shorter hours (although this also constitutes child labour in the broader sense).

3 Methods

Given a true risk p_{jk} of a child being engaged in the binary outcome k ($k = 0, 1, 2, 3$) at cluster j with location x_j , the number of children observed to be engaged in outcome k at cluster j was assumed to follow a binomial distribution

$$Y_{jk} \sim \text{Binomial}(n_j, p_{jk})$$

where n_j is the number of children surveyed at cluster j . The risk p_{jk} is modelled according to the joint specification

$$\begin{aligned} \text{logit}(p_{j0}) &= u_{j0} + S_0(x_j) & k = 0 \\ \text{logit}(p_{jk}) &= u_{jk} + S_0(x_j) + S_k(x_j) & k = 1, 2, 3 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where u_{jk} is an independent and identically distributed (IID) non-spatial Gaussian random effect, S_0 is a spatially structured random effect shared across all four outcomes, and S_k for $k = 1, 2, 3$ is

a spatially structured outcome-specific effect. In this research, the number of children in the lowest wealth quintile is the outcome corresponding to $k = 0$ and is essentially the “baseline” outcome, against which excess risks of other outcomes are assessed. This specification is similar to that of Palmí-Perales et al. (2021), who used a multivariate approach to model spatial point patterns of disease cases, taking controls as a baseline outcome.

All spatial effects S_k are assumed to be Gaussian processes with covariances given by the Matérn covariance function, which depends on the Euclidean distance ($\|.\|$) between two locations x_i and x_j :

$$Cov(S(x_i), S(x_j)) = \frac{\sigma^2}{2^{\nu-1}\Gamma(\nu)} (\kappa\|x_i - x_j\|)^{\nu} K_{\nu}(\kappa\|x_i - x_j\|) \quad (2)$$

where σ^2 is the marginal variance of the process S , κ is a spatial scaling parameter, ν is a smoothness parameter and K_{ν} is the modified Bessel function of the second kind and order ν . The SPDE numerical approximation of S_k was implemented using INLA with R packages R-INLA and inlabru (Rue et al., 2009; Lindgren et al., 2011; Bachl et al., 2019).

Table 1: Mean, standard deviation (SD), and 95% credible interval (95% CI) of posterior distributions of hyperparameters of spatial (SPDE) and non-spatial random effects for all outcomes.

Hyperparameter	Outcome	Mean	SD	95% CI
SPDE range	LWQ	173.0602	16.3056	(143.837, 207.9813)
	OOS	234.8225	59.1389	(143.4277, 374.5933)
	CL	771.0665	200.7864	(458.8493, 1243.7201)
	Haz. work	676.9198	177.5369	(401.861, 1095.7407)
SPDE std. dev.	LWQ	1.7710	0.1236	(1.545, 2.0314)
	OOS	1.2108	0.1444	(0.9547, 1.5225)
	CL	1.5055	0.3203	(0.9862, 2.2416)
	Haz. work	1.4952	0.3153	(0.983, 2.2187)
Random eff. precision	LWQ	0.3273	0.0234	(0.2835, 0.3755)
	OOS	0.8248	0.0773	(0.6825, 0.9864)
	CL	17.7496	6.9511	(8.6172, 35.3931)
	Haz. work	5.7288	1.0778	(3.9705, 8.1964)

Figure 1: Spatial distribution of estimated outcome-specific spatial effects (S_k). Means and standard deviations of spatial effects are shown.

4 Results

Table 1 summarises the posterior distributions of the random effects for each outcome, including the shared spatial effect of the baseline outcome, the number of children in the lowest wealth quintile (LWQ). Comparing the ranges of the spatial effects, that of the out of school outcome is smaller than both that of the child labour and hazardous work specific effects. This suggests a more local spatial effect than for the other two outcomes. The ranges of the child labour and hazardous work specific

spatial effects are similar, indicating that these two effects operate at similar spatial scales.

The spatial distributions of the mean and standard deviation of the posterior estimates of the specific spatial effects S_1 , S_2 and S_3 are shown in Figure 1, along with the zonal administrative boundaries of Nigeria. These specific spatial effects are considered relative to the baseline spatial effect, with a positive or negative value indicating a child is at more or less risk, respectively, of engaging in each outcome than of being in the lowest wealth quintile. While the spatial distributions are all different, there are some similarities with the relative risk of all three outcomes being high in the centres of the North-West and North-Central (around Abuja) zones, and in the west of the South-South zone. Some areas of notable difference are the east of the South-South zone, where the risk of a child being out of school is lower than that of them being in the lowest wealth quintile but the risk of both child labour and engaging in hazardous work is higher, and the north of the North-East zone, where the risk of a child being out of school is relatively high but the risk of hazardous work is low and that of child labour is similar to the risk of a child being in the lowest wealth quintile. In general, the child labour specific spatial effect is positive across most of the study area, implying that there is generally a greater risk of a child engaging in child labour than being in the lowest wealth quintile, although the strength of this excess risk varies.

The total risk of all outcomes was predicted across Nigeria by using both the baseline spatial effect S_0 and the outcome-specific spatial effects S_k . The non-spatial random effects u_{jk} were accounted for in the predictions by sampling from the posterior distribution. Figure 2 shows the spatial distribution of the estimated risks. There is a clear difference in the risk of a child being out of school between the north and the south of Nigeria, with almost all areas of the South-West, South-East and South-South zones having a less than 20% risk of children being out of school. This pattern is not as clear for the risks of children engaging in child labour or hazardous work, however, with the very low risk areas being concentrated in the South-West zone and along the border between the South-West and South-South zones. As might be expected, the risk of a child engaging in hazardous work is generally lower than that of them engaging in child labour and this was found to be particularly noticeable in the east of the country. However, in areas where the risk of hazardous work was highest, the levels of risk were similar to those of the risk of child labour, suggesting that children are more likely to undertake hazardous types of work in these locations.

5 Conclusion

This work demonstrates how multivariate spatial methods can be used to model excess risks of child labour and school attendance. The results have shown that the spatial distribution of lowest wealth quintile households does differ from that of the other outcomes studied. It is hoped that identifying areas with excess risk of out of school children, child labour, or children in hazardous work can help motivate and direct future research to help better understand the context around these excess risks. This study also predicted out of school and child labour levels at a high spatial resolution. Such spatial analysis is lacking in the child labour literature but is important so that interventions and policies can be properly informed.

Figure 2: Predicted risk of a child being out of school, meeting the threshold of hours for child labour, and engaging in hazardous work. Means and standard deviations are shown.

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Biography

Tom Cunningham is currently a PhD student on the Data Analytics and Society CDT programme at the University of Manchester. His research is focused on spatial analysis and spatial modelling, with his PhD exploring how these methodologies can be applied to better understand child labour and its related factors globally.

Nuno Pinto is Senior Lecturer in Urban Planning and Urban Design at the School of Environment, Education and Development of The University of Manchester. His main research interests focus on the use of quantitative approaches to urban planning, including decision support in urban planning, urban simulation, and quantitative methods.

Wendy Olsen is Professor of Socio-Economics at the University of Manchester and was previously head of the Department of Social Statistics. Her research focuses on the sociology of economic life. She has interests in methodology across the whole range from quantitatively based to qualitative research and discourse analysis.

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